

deletion and that the Myanma RTBV isolates belong to the Southeast Asian strain.

PCR products of both isolates were sequenced directly using the same PCR primers. Nucleotide sequences were compared with other RTBV isolates (see figure). Only 3 positions (7765, 7768, and 7855), which represent only 1.5% of the region sequenced, of both isolates, were different from the published sequence of the Philippine isolate. The Indian isolate differs significantly from other Southeast Asian isolates, the homology being less than 80%. The Baular isolate has a transition of T (C at position 7853 and a deletion at position 7956, a structure that differentiates it from the Amara-pura and other isolates. Ambiguities found at positions 7858, 7870, 7921, 7945, and 7949 may reflect the level of variation of the virus within the isolate. This information is only found if PCR products of viral DNA are sequenced, because cloning would result in selection of only one variant per clone.

These results demonstrate that tungro is present in Myanmar. The symptoms were characteristic of the disease and occurred in patches in the fields. The results also support the versatility of this PCR approach in the identification of RTBV itself and the strain of the virus. ■

	7758				7806
JII	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGATA	CGAACTAAGT	TTCTTATGAA
JAP	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGATA	AGAACTAAGT	ATCTTATGAA
MY6	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGGTA	GGAACTAAGT	ATCTTATGAA
BEA	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGATG	AGAACTAAGT	ATCTTATGAA
MY10	AATACCCT.A	TAGATGTTAG	AAGGAAGGTA	GGAACTAAGT	ATCTTATGAA
IND	AATACCCTAA	TAAGTGCTAG	AAGGAAGATA	AGAACTAACG	AAATAAGGAA
	7807				7854
JII	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..T	CGTTATAATC
JAP	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..C	CGTTATAATC
MY6	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..T	CGTTATAATC
BEA	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..T	CGTTATAATC
MY10	CAATGGGTAG	CTGATTTCTG	ATTATCATT	ACAAGTA..T	CGTTATAATC
IND	CATTGGGTAG	CTGTTTCTG	ATTATCATT	TCAAGTAGCT	CTTCCTCATC
	7855				7903
JII	CATAAGCTTT	GAAAGATCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
JAP	CATAAGCTTT	GAAAGATCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
MY6	TATRAGCTTT	GAAAGTCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
BEA	CATAAGCTTT	GAAAGATCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
MY10	TATRAGCTCT	GAAAGTCTG	.CTAGTGTGG	ATACCAAAG	GCTGTCGTGG
IND	ACGAAAACCTG	CAAAGGCTG	CCAACCCTAG	GCTGAAAACAG	TGACTAGGCC
	7904				7953
JII	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGATGA	GGTCATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TAGGTAACCTA
JAP	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGATGA	GGTCATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TAGGTAACCTA
MY6	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGAYGA	GTTATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TMGGTWACTA
BEA	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGATGA	GGTCATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TAGGTAACCTA
MY10	TTCGCCAGT	CGACGGATGA	GTTATAAAC	GAAGCACTAG	TAGGTAACCTA
IND	GAGGAATTGC	GAAAAGATAG	GGGGGTGCC	GCATC.....
	7954				7892
JII	AGAGGCTTA	GGGATGAAGCA	ACGAGAAAA		
JAP	AGAGGCTTA	GGGATGA.GCA	ACGAGAAAA		
MY6	AGAGGCTTA	GGGATGA.GCA	ACGAGAAAA		
BEA	AGAGGCTTA	GGGATGA.GCA	ACGAGAAAA		
MY10	AGAGGCTTA	AGGATGA.GCA	ACGAGAAAA		
IND

Nucleotide sequence comparison across the positions 7758-7982. JII, JAP, and BEA are published sequences of RTBV isolates from the Philippines. IND is unpublished sequence of RTBV isolate from India (West Bengal), MY6 is the Amara-pura isolate, and MY10 is the Baular isolate. White letters indicate differences found in isolates from Myanmar; bold letters are ambiguities expressed as IUB codes found in the sequences of PCR products.

Hinosan (0.05%): an ecofriendly fungicide for managing rice sheath blight

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Sheath blight (ShB) is a major fungal disease of rice in northeastern India. There are no ShB-resistant varieties for that region, so chemical management is used. Recently, more attention has been paid to chemicals that would not have a negative impact on microorganisms endogenous to the rice crop ecosystem.

In 1994 and 1995, we screened fungicides known to be effective against ShB

but harmless to *Trichoderma harzianum* (Th), which is a well-known biocontrol agent of the causal agent of ShB, *Rhizoctonia solani*.

Seven fungicides were tested: Atemi 50 SL (cyproconazole), Bavistin 50 WP (carbendazim), Contaf (hexaconazole), Indofil M-45 (75% mancozeb), Hinosan (50%, edifenphos), Rhizolex 50 WP (tolelofoxmethyl), and Validacin 3L (validamycin). Treatments included recommended doses and half doses, which were tested in vitro and in vivo.

Results of the in vitro experiment indicated that, except for 0.05% Hinosan (8% inhibition), all fungicides showed inhibited Th within the range

of 31.8-92%. Hinosan (0.05%) showed no significant difference in inhibition and was equivalent to the control. When tested against the pathogen in vitro, all fungicides, including Hinosan (0.05%), showed significant inhibition compared with the untreated control (see table).

In the following winter rice seasons (Jun-Nov) of 1994 and 1995, two field trials were conducted on rainfed transplanted rice. Variety IR50 was selected and planted in two lines (20 × 15 cm) for each treatment with 2-m rows replicated three times.

In the first trial (A), the same fungicides, doses, and concentrations

Effect of fungicides (in vitro) on the growth of *Trichoderma harzianum* (Th) and *Rhizoctonia solani* (Rs)^a and disease severity^b of ShB.

Fungicide	Dose (%)	% inhibition of Th (mean)	% inhibition of Rs (mean)	Disease score	
				A (in vivo test I)	B (in vivo test II)
Atemi 50 SL	0.2	77.1 cd	75.1 de	3.7 a	4.3 b
Atemi 50 SL	0.1	31.8 b	49.0 c	5.0 bc	5.6 d
Bavistin 50 WP	0.1	79.5 cd	71.1 d	3.7 a	4.3 b
Bavistin 50 WP	0.05	65.1 c	53.4 c	4.3 ab	5.0 c
Contaf 5 EC	0.2	92.0 d	88.8 f	3.0 a	3.6 a
Contaf 5 EC	0.1	74.5 cd	71.7 d	4.3 ab	5.0 c
Indofil M-45	0.25	69.1 c	75.1 d	4.3 ab	5.6 d
Indofil M-45	0.125	48.4 bc	22.5 b	5.7 c	7.0 e
Hinosan 50 EC	0.1	43.4 bc	84.1 ef	3.7 a	3.6 a
Hinosan 50 EC	0.05	8.0 a	78.4 de	4.1 a	3.6 a
Rhizolex 50 WP	0.2	77.2 cd	72.7 d	4.3 ab	3.6 a
Rhizolex 50 WP	0.1	59.9 c	58.0 c	5.0 bc	5.0 c
Validacin 3L	0.2	76.4 cd	87.6 f	3.0 a	3.6 a
Validacin 3L	0.1	41.6 bc	54.5 c	5.0 bc	4.3 b
Control	-	0 a	0 a	8.3 d	8.3 f
Standard check	10 ⁶ conidia mL ⁻¹	-	-	-	5.6 d
LSD (0.05)		15.82	7.17	0.39	0.51
CV (%)		15.34	9.1	11.56	14.7

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. All data are means of three replications. ^b Scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice scale* 0-9. 1988.

were used and the plants were artificially inoculated with *R. solani*. Five sprays were done at weekly intervals beginning from the first appearance of the disease after 7 d of

inoculation. Contaf (0.2%) and Validacin (0.2%) showed the lowest disease severity, followed by Atemi (0.2%), Bavistin (0.1%), and Hinosan (0.1 and 0.05%) (see table).

In the second trial (B), the above treatments were used in combination with spray of the antagonist (Th) (106 conidia mL⁻¹). The sprays were initiated with the respective fungicides as the disease appeared and after. Thus, out of five sprays, two sprays were made with the antagonist (see table). An additional treatment (standard check) was included in this test where all five sprays were done with the antagonist alone. In this second field test (B), Th alone suppressed the disease compared with the unprotected control. The lowest disease severity was recorded when Th was combined with Contaf (0.2%), Hinosan (0.1 and 0.05%), Rhizolex (0.2%), and Validacin (0.2%). The combined treatment of Hinosan (0.05%) with the biocontrol agent was found to be an exception and Hinosan (0.05%) in both the experiments controlled the disease. As the effect of Hinosan (0.05%) on Th had been documented in an earlier experiment, it is suggested for inclusion in the integrated pest management strategy to control ShB. ■

Integrated pest management – insects

Record of *Aspergillus terreus* Thom. on rice grasshopper *Hieroglyphus banian* (F.) in India

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In a series of surveys on fungal diseases of rice insects in general and leafhopper in particular during the 1996 samba season (October through February) at Annamalainagar, 40% of the rice grasshopper (*Hieroglyphus banian* [F.]) population was found to be infected with a fungal pathogen.

Nymphs and adults were diseased. The cadavers were dull and brownish yellow and were seen holding the rice culms with their legs, with the insects' heads pointing toward the shoot tips (see figure). Abundant mycelial growth

***Aspergillus terreus* infecting the final nymphal instar of rice grasshopper.**

was observed at the intersegmental regions of the thorax and the abdomen but not the head capsule. On continued exposure to sunlight, the cadavers dried and the fungal matrix withered off.

The cadavers were gathered from the field, surface-sterilized with 0.1% HgCl₂ for 1-2 min, and washed in sterile water. The organism was inoculated in Sabouraud maltose agar

(SMA) medium on petri plates and incubated at 25±1 °C for 15 d. The fungal colonies appeared 5 d after inoculation and the culture was initially pale yellow or bright yellow, and ultimately deep brown.

Pathogenicity testing of the fungus isolated was done by spraying its spore suspension (107 spores mL⁻¹) over nymphs (second- and third-instar) and adults caged separately on IR50 rice plants grown in pots. The experiment was replicated three times using 10 insects replication⁻¹ and three replications of a control receiving plain water spray. Mean mortality of the grasshoppers was recorded as 85%, in 4-5 d after spraying (see table). The fungus from the diseased cadavers was reisolated in SMA medium and the disease symptoms that developed were identical to those of the original cadavers gathered at the start. The